

**PURPOSE AND TASKS OF ORGANIZING INCLUSIVE EDUCATION
(AS AN EXAMPLE OF THE EDUCATIONAL PROCESS OF STUDENTS
WITH HEARING AND VISUAL IMPAIRMENTS AND MENTAL
RETARDATION)**

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Abstract. In this article, the information about what tasks should be set before the pedagogue in organizing the process of education and upbringing with children with disabilities in general education schools is highlighted.

Key words: education, upbringing, inclusive, hearing impaired, speech impaired, visually impaired, mentally retarded children.

Development of inclusive education in Uzbekistan in accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 29, 2019 "On approval of the concept of development of the public education system of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" No. PF-5712, a decision was made to improve the system of education for children with special educational needs and to improve the quality of educational services provided to them.

The goal of inclusive education is to create a barrier-free, adapted educational environment for students with special educational needs, by using special tools and methods at school, involving special pedagogues, their effective adaptation to society and full-fledged development. is to provide quality general secondary education that serves the harmonization.

Schools provide comprehensive support to children with special educational needs and their parents in receiving corrective pedagogical support and career guidance.

The tasks of inclusive education are as follows:

- creation of a single adapted social environment for students with different development opportunities, which excludes any discrimination and ensures equal treatment of all children;
- - formation of a tolerant attitude towards the problems of students with special educational needs in the public and all participants of the educational process;
- - creating an opportunity for all students to master general secondary education programs in accordance with state educational standards;

- creating conditions for all-round development of students, activation of emotional and volitional sphere, cognitive activity, formation of social skills and potential;
- to provide counseling support to families raising children with special educational needs and to raise the level of awareness of parents in the field of education and upbringing of their children, pedagogical technologies, methods and tools of education and training, psychological and pedagogical training consists of support.

In our country, favorable conditions are being created for the education and upbringing of children with disabilities and their adaptation to social life. In order to integrate them into the society, first of all, in order to restore their health as much as possible, work is being carried out on the basis of the "General education project for children with disabilities".

This mainly involves the use of inclusive education opportunities. Deeper study of inclusive education, identification of problems related to it, justification of efficiency aspects is becoming an urgent scientific problem. Because the inclusive education method provides a convenient opportunity to ensure the full participation of all children in the educational process, regardless of their mental and physical condition.

In particular, it is necessary for children with special needs to communicate with others, grow up to be able to meet the demands of the social environment, acquire the skills to meet their daily and household needs, adapt to life and have healthy peers in general education schools. creates facilities for him to be able to study under equal conditions, to enter into a friendly relationship with them, to master the lessons on time, to approach assignments responsibly.

When conducting classes with children with special needs in general education schools, the pedagogue should carefully organize the educational process. In particular, the pedagogue is required to be careful and considerate when conducting educational activities with children with disabilities (hearing and vision problems, as well as retarded mental development).

The pedagogues have the following tasks in organizing the educational process with hearing-impaired children:

- it is necessary to know in time the changes in the speech and mentality of children who cannot hear well;
- in order to find out the level of the child's hearing ability, if necessary, it is necessary to send him to a specialist otolaryngologist for treatment;

- the most important thing is to always remember that there is a child in the class who does not hear very well and to put such children on the 1st desk;
- - when the pedagogue is explaining the topic to the students of the class, while reading the dictation text, he should see how well the student understands the topic.

II. Working with students with speech disabilities

The teacher should pay attention to the following:

- the pedagogue should pay special attention to students with incorrect pronunciation and seek advice from speech therapists;
- - not to offend the child by giving a low grade for his mistakes in reading and writing, to encourage him, to support him, to make concessions, and to use the principles of education and training, such as tolerance, and to rely on the positive aspects of his behavior, it is necessary to instill in him the idea that difficulties can be overcome.

III. The pedagogue's role in working with visually impaired students:

- if there is a student in the class who does not see well, it is necessary to contact his parents first and recommend that he be shown to an ophthalmologist (ophthalmologist);
- sometimes the child's parents try to hide their blindness. It is important to remember that showing off in normal school conditions can have bad consequences. The teacher should also explain these aspects to the parents.

IV. The task of the teacher in working with mentally retarded children

- to be able to distinguish between the cognitive activities of mentally retarded children studying in general education schools and the cognitive activities of healthy children;
- failure to apply the educational program requirements for a healthy child to a mentally retarded child;
- to assign tasks to mentally retarded children in the course of the lesson that match their ability to learn;
- to encourage and support the child, taking into account some of his achievements, without following him among the students so that he does not master the lessons;
- the process of teaching mentally retarded children in general education schools requires a high level of professional and personal ability for the pedagogue. It is important for the pedagogue to work in cooperation with the children's parents, to work with them in the course of the lesson, taking into

account the characteristics of their children. Because children with mental retardation do not have a stable mentality, they change in insignificant situations and situations, quick irritability is characteristic of their nature.

We can see that it has a positive effect on the physical and mental condition of children with disabilities based on the following requirements. It should not be forgotten that inclusive education not only helps the child to study together with his peers, but also gives him the opportunity to socialize with them in society.

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